

STOL TENNISINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATI NIMADA?

Умуркулова Дилрабо Абдисаматовна

УЗМУ, Таэквондо ва спорт фаолияти факультети

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10425906>

Аннотация. *Ushbu maqola stol tennis va uning ijobiy va samarali diqqatga sazovor joylari haqida ma'lumotni o'z ichiga oladi, bu ular haqida ma'lumotga ega bo'lgan ikki tur. Tennis, asl nomi maysazor tennis, ikkita qarama-qarshi o'yinchi (yakkalik) yoki juft o'yinchi (juftlik) belgilangan o'lchamdagi, og'irlikdagi to'pni urish va to'rtburchaklar kortda to'r ustidan sakrash uchun tarang tortilgan raketkalaridan foydalanadigan o'yin. Raqib to'pni belgilangan maydon o'lchamlari doirasida to'g'ri qaytara olmasa, o'yinchi yoki jamoaga ballar beriladi.*

Калит сўзлар: sport, tennis, o'yinchilar, jamoa, sportchilar.

WHAT IS SPECIAL ABOUT TABLE TENNIS?

Abstract. *This article contains information about table tennis and its positive and effective sights, it's two types with information about them. Tennis, original name lawn tennis, game in which two opposing players (singles) or pairs of players (doubles) use tautly strung rackets to hit a ball of specified size, weight, and bounce over a net on a rectangular court. Points are awarded to a player or team whenever the opponent fails to correctly return the ball within the prescribed dimensions of the court.*

Key words: sport, tennis, players, team, athletes.

ЧТО ОСОБЕННОГО В НАСТОЛЬНОМ ТЕННИСЕ?

Аннотация. *Эта статья содержит информацию о теннисе и его положительных и эффективных аспектах, это два типа с информацией о них. Теннис, оригинальное название лаун-теннис, игра, в которой два игрока-соперника (одиночные) или пары игроков (парные) используют туго натянутые ракетки, чтобы отбить мяч определенного размера, веса и отскочить от сетки на прямоугольном корте. Очки начисляются игроку или команде всякий раз, когда соперник не может правильно вернуть мяч в пределах предписанных размеров площадки.*

Ключевые слова: спорт, теннис, игроки, команда, спортсмены.

Table tennis, also called (trademark) Ping-Pong, ball game similar in principle to lawn tennis and played on a flat table divided into two equal courts by a net fixed across its width at the middle. The object is to hit the ball so that it goes over the net and bounces on the opponent's half of the table in such a way that the opponent cannot reach it or return it correctly. The lightweight hollow ball is propelled back and forth across the net by small rackets (bats, or paddles) held by the players.

The game is popular all over the world. In most countries it is very highly organized as a competitive sport, especially in Europe and Asia, particularly in China and Japan.

History. The game was invented in England in the early days of the 20th century and was originally called Ping-Pong, a trade name. The name table tennis was adopted in 1921–22 when the old Ping-Pong Association formed in 1902 was revived. The original association had broken up about 1905, though apparently the game continued to be played in parts of England outside London and by the 1920s was being played in many countries.

Led by representatives of Germany, Hungary, and England, the Fédération Internationale de Tennis de Table (International Table Tennis Federation) was founded in 1926, the founding members being England, Sweden, Hungary, India, Denmark, Germany, Czechoslovakia, Austria, and Wales. By the mid-1990s more than 165 national associations were members.

The first world championships were held in London in 1926, and from then until 1939 the game was dominated by players from central Europe, the men's team event being won nine times by Hungary and twice by Czechoslovakia. In the mid-1950s Asia emerged as a breeding ground of champions, and from that time the individual and team events (for both men and women) have been dominated by athletes from China. The popularity of the game in China was notable for giving rise to so-called "Ping-Pong diplomacy," a period during the 1970s in which Cold War tensions between China and the United States were eased via a series of highly publicized table tennis matches between athletes from the two countries. The first such event—held in Beijing in 1971—is widely credited with paving the way for U.S. Pres. Richard Nixon's historic visit to China the following year.

In 1980 the first World Cup was held, and Guo Yuehua of China won the \$12,500 first prize. Table tennis became an Olympic sport in 1988, with singles and doubles competition for men and women.

Table tennis is a fast-paced, competitive game that requires quick reflexes and great hand-eye coordination. It's also one of the most commonly played sports around the world today! Although it may sound like a complicated sport to play, table tennis actually only takes minutes to learn.

Table Tennis is a game played on a flat table divided into two courts by a net. The lightweight hollow ball is propelled back and forth across the net by small rackets (bats, or paddles) held by the players. It is a fast-paced sport that requires quick reflexes and great hand-eye coordination.

In normal play, the aim is to return the ball onto your opponents side of the table, only allowing it to bounce on your side once before hitting the ball with your racket. You win a point if your opponent fails to return the ball onto your side of the table.

Table Tennis can be played as singles (one person playing against another) or doubles (two people playing on each side) where players have to make alternate shots. Table tennis is loosely based on a parlour game played in the 1880s by British Army officers stationed in India and South Africa. Their game was almost unrecognisable from the sport played today, using cigar box lids as bats and rounded wine bottle corks for balls.

The game is naturally similar to a combination of both tennis and badminton, which were popular at the end of the 19th century. The early form of the sport was called Ping-Pong by most players. However, the name of this new game became a problem because it was also the name of an existing tabletop game made and copyrighted by Parker Brothers (in America). Ultimately, the name table tennis was adopted in 1921 and has become the most widely known name for the sport. It wasn't until 1901 that the hollow celluloid ball was introduced, immediately gaining popularity around the world. Along with a new ball, the first rules were published in 1901. The first world championships were then held in London in 1926, the same year that the International Table Tennis Federation (ITTF) was formed.

The table tennis official rules that we know today are set forth by the ITTF, who were the first to come up with a uniform rule that all countries would adopt. This rule is called “Table Tennis: The Official Rulebook” and it has been revised three times, most recently in 2003.

The rackets used today are very different to those used in the early days of the sport. It was 1959 when the ITTF defined the first set of rules, requiring all rackets to be a piece of wood sandwiched by a thin sponge layer and rubber. Check out our full history of table tennis from 1890’s to Present Day or how the table tennis ball has changed dramatically since those early days.

Discovering any new sport can be quite daunting, especially with lots of new words you may not have seen before. Fortunately, Table Tennis is quite a simple game, so there are only a few new terms that you need to learn:

- Forehand: A shot played on your dominant side, with your elbow pointing away from your opponent.
- Backhand: A shot played from your non-dominant side, with forearm perpendicular to your opponent and elbow pointing out to the side.
- Rally: A series of consecutive successful hits of the ball made by 1 or 2 players on either side of the table.
- Let: Used when a ball hits the net and rolls over onto the receivers side of the table during the service, or when a point is interrupted and discontinued during a rally.
- Point: Won whenever a player is unable to return the ball successfully during a rally.

Table. All official Table Tennis tables have to have the same dimensions, or you’ll find yourself missing the table a lot! That is, the playing height needs to be 76cm (29.92 inches), the length should be 273cm (107.48 inches), whilst the width is 152.5 cm (107.48 inches).

The tables themselves can be made of pretty much anything, although most tables you can buy will have wooden tops. They can also be painted / colored any color you like, although the common colours are dark blue / dark green because it’s much easier to see the ball on those colors.

Net. The net is comprised of 2 net posts and a long mesh fabric strung up in the middle of the table. The net should always be 15.25 cm (6 inches) tall, with a reasonable tension pulling at either sides so it doesn’t droop / dip in the middle.

You’ll find all different kind of nets available around the world, including clip-on and metal nets. As long as you have a divider roughly 15cm tall, you’ll definitely still be able to enjoy a game of Table Tennis!

Ball. The ball you use must be spherical, with a diameter of 40mm and a weight of 2.7g. They are most commonly made of celluloid or a very similar plastic composition and must either white or orange.

Table Tennis balls come in a few different types, depending on the quality specifications they are made on. Yep, some of them are less ‘round’ than others! The most common types are ‘training’ balls, 1-star, 2-star and 3-star balls. If you want to play competitively, most tournaments will always use a 3-star ball. For anyone just starting out, cheaper training balls will feel almost exactly the same.

Racket/ Bat / Paddle. After playing Table Tennis for over 15 years, I can safely say you’re allowed to call the racket any name you want! Many people call it bat / paddle / racket all across

the world. All rackets should consist of a wooden blade in the centre, with a layer of sponge and a layer of rubber on each side.

The fun part with rackets is that they can be any size, shape or weight meaning that super-sized rackets are legally allowed in competition! Not that it would help you too much.

You'll occasionally find plastic or wooden rackets, although I wouldn't advise playing with these as they struggle to impart any spin onto the ball which is a key part of the sport.

Table tennis is one of the world's fastest-growing sports, played by millions of people every day. In fact, there are close to 300 million table tennis players in China alone! That is almost twice as many in any other country. I personally love the sport because of the competitive 1 on 1 nature, relying on your own skill and ability to beat your opponent both tactically and mentally. Playing can be both incredibly challenging, as well as incredibly fun with Table Tennis being really enjoyable at a bar with a few drinks. Ignoring those few drinks, Table Tennis can also have many great health benefits as you need to be constantly moving whilst playing.

It's also a sport that people can play for their entire lives because it does not rely on natural quickness or speed but instead relies more heavily on technique and strategy. I've played (and lost) against people in their 80s who are still going strong. You get a whole spectrum of play with Table Tennis as it can be played with friends in the backyard or at home, whilst there are also many competitive tournaments that take place all over the world! Whilst you may never get to the level of the best table tennis players ever, it's such a fun sport to play at all skill levels.

Is Table Tennis a hard sport? Table Tennis is a very simple sport to understand and play. It is very easy to learn the basic rules and moves, but it takes a lot of practice in order to perfect your form – this is what makes table tennis so difficult when you play against more experienced players!

Table Tennis requires that you have quick reflexes when defending against aggressive shots from your opponent. You often have very little time to react, with the distance between players being only around 3 metres. That's where the tactical nature of the sport is important, positioning yourself where you expect the opponent to hit the ball.

When you play against better players, you'll also find a lot of spin gets imparted on the ball. Without a lot of practise and training, it can be very difficult to read and understand this spin. With that all being said, if you want to play a casual game with a mate in your garden, it's a very simple, relaxing and enjoyable sport.

REFERENCES

1. Umurkulova D. A. TA'LIM JARAYONINI AXBOROTLASHTIRISHDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING AFZALLIKLARI //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 5-2. – С. 314-318.
2. Umurkulova D. A. DYNAMICS OF PHYSICAL TRAINING OF TABLE TENNIS PEOPLE IN PRIMARY PREPARATORY GROUPS //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 11. – С. 168-177.
3. Rakhmatillayev M. METHODS OF SELECTING TALENTED CHILDREN FOR HANDBALL SPORT //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. - 2022. - Т. 2. - №. 11. - С. 935-939.

4. Rahimov V.Sh. Zamonaviy jamiyatda jismoniy tarbiya va sportning ijtimoiy vazifalari. Ta'lim fanlaridagi tadqiqotlar va mulohazalarning Yevropa jurnali, jild. 8 Yo'q. 12, 2020 III qism ISSN 2056-5852.
5. Rahimov V.Sh. Jismoniy tarbiya bo'yicha mutaxassislar tayyorlash sifatini oshirishga innovatsion yandashuvlar. Ta'lim fanlaridagi tadqiqotlar va mulohazalarning Yevropa jurnali, jild. 8 Yo'q. 12, 2020, 225-230.
6. Rakhimov V.Sh. Social functions of physical culture and sports in modern society. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 8 No. 12, 2020 Part III ISSN 2056-5852.
7. Rakhimov V.Sh. Innovative approaches to improving quality training specialists in physical education. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 8 No. 12, 2020, 225-230.
8. RAXIMOV V. Social functions of physical culture and sports in modern society //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2020.
9. RAXIMOV V. Innovative approaches to improving quality training specialists in physical education //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2020.
10. Arzibayev K. O., Sh R. V. Effects On Performance By Electronic Training Equipment For Young Karatists.« //Psychologi and education» Journal. – 2021. – T. 58. – №. 2. – С. 11488-11490.
11. Arzibayev K. O. V. Sh. Rahimov Influence of Basketball on the Mental and Physical Development of the Personality.« //International Journal of Future of Generation Communication and Networking. – 2021. – T. 14. – №. 1. – С. 768-772.
12. Ziyadullaev K. S. et al. Creation of a model of development of sports marketing in modernization of sports management system in Uzbekistan //Journal of Physical Education and Sport. – 2022. – T. 22. – №. 1. – С. 19-25.
13. РАХИМОВ В. РАЗВИТИЕ ЖИЗНЕННО ВАЖНЫХ НАВЫКОВ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ У СТУДЕНТОВ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПУТИ ЕГО РЕШЕНИЯ //http://science. nuu.uz/uzmu. php.
14. Rakhimov V. S. MODERN APPROACHES TO SPORTS AND HEALTH TOURISM TRAINING //Conferencea. – 2021. – С. 42-46.
15. RAXIMOV V. Social functions of physical culture and sports in modern society //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2020.
16. Elmuradova M. U., Rakhimov V. S. EFFICIENCY OF USING NATIONAL AND ACTIVE GAMES IN PHYSICAL TRAINING AND SPORTS PRACTICES //Актуальные проблемы физического воспитания студентов. – 2022. – С. 176-177.
17. Khahhorova X., Rakhimov V. S. NON-TRADITIONAL PHYSICAL TRAINING AND SPORTS MANAGEMENT //Актуальные проблемы физического воспитания студентов. – 2022. – С. 170-172.
18. Akparov F. M., Inogamov I. I., Rakhimov V. S. THE PHYSICAL OF THE YOUNG GENERATION THROUGH MOVING GAMES DEVELOPING PREPARATION. – 2021.
19. Inogamov I. I., Sobirova K. A., Rakhimov V. S. THE QUESTION ABOUT THE METHODOLOGY OF LEARNING HAND STANDS. – 2021.

20. Akparov F. M., Khasanova I. K., Rakhimov V. S. THE ESSENCE OF SPORT MARKETING. – 2021.
21. Rakhimov V. S., Akparov F. M., Inogamov I. I. PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING OF PERSPECTIVE ATHLETES AT THE MODERN STAGE //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ УСЛОВИЯХ. – 2021. – С. 469-472.
21. Холов В. А., Рахимов В. Ш., Симаков Д. В. ОБЗОР ПРОСТРАНСТВЕННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКИ АКТИВНЫХ ТОЧЕК //XCVI Международных научных чтений (памяти ГН Бабакина). – 2020. – С. 31-35.
22. Shavkatovich R. V. INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO IMPROVING QUALITY TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2020. – Т. 8. – №. 2.
23. RAXIMOV V. Innovative approaches to improving quality training specialists in physical education //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2020.
24. Shavkatovich R. V. SOCIAL FUNCTIONS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN MODERN SOCIETY.
25. Shavkatovich R. V. INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO IMPROVING QUALITY TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2020. – Т. 8. – №. 2.
26. Давурбаева М. Ж., Казоқов Р. Т., Мадаминов М. П. ТАЛАБА ЁШЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМ ОЛИШДАГИ БИЛИМ ВА КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИНГ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШДА ИНТЕРНЕТ РЕСУРСЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 26-31.
27. Давурбаева М. Ж., Казоқов Р. Т., Мадаминов М. П. ТАЛАБА ЁШЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМ ОЛИШДАГИ БИЛИМ ВА КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИНГ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШДА ИНТЕРНЕТ РЕСУРСЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 26-31.
28. Давурбаева М.Ж.,Казоқов Р.Т., Мадаминов М.П.Ёшларнинг мустақил таълим олишдаги билим ва кўникмаларининг такомиллаштиришда интернет ресурсларидан фойдаланишнинг ахамияти//ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE. - 2023/2/14. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 26-31.
29. Казоқов Р. Т., Жўрақўзиев О. О., Эшпўлатов С. С. СПОРТ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 13. – С. 238-248.
30. Казоқов Р.Т., Бўриев Б.Ў., Абдиев Б.Ш., Джўрабаев А.М., Туропов А.Р.КУРАШ МИЛЛИЙ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ // МИЛЛИЙ КУРАШ ТУРЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ-АМАЛИЙ МУАММОЛАРИ. - 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 161-163.

31. Джўрабаев А. М., Казоқов Р. Т. Биомеханик таҳлиллар асосида энгил атлетикачиларнинг функционал тайёргарлигидаги корреляция алоқаларининг таҳлили //Yoshlarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va aholi salomatligini mustahkamlash yili” ga bag ‘ishlangan. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 198-208.
32. Казоқов Р. Т., Расулов А. Ф., Бўронов А. Б. СПОРТ МАКТАБЛАРИ ЎҚУВ-МАШҒУЛОТ ГУРУҲЛАРИДА ЁШ ФУТБОЛЧИЛАРНИ ТАНЛОВ УСЛУБИЯТЛАРИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 15. – С. 38-46.
33. Kazoqov R. T., Bo'ronov A. B. SPORTDAGI DOLZARB YANGILIKLAR //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 15. – С. 47-56.
34. Kazoqov R. T., Pirnazarov S. A., Shamsiddinov S. X. STUDENTS LEARN TO ORGANIZE PROFESSIONAL PHYSICAL TRAINING AND CONTROL PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1195-1202.
35. Eshpo'latov S. S. METHODS AND PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS AND PHYSICAL TRAINING OF YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1296-1302.
36. Kazoqov R. T., Eshpo'latov S. S. YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS ARE THE PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING TRAINING SESSIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1303-1310.
37. Pirmatov O. Z., Kazakov R. T. ROLE AND PLACE OF SPORTS AND ACTIVE GAMES IN THE GENERAL STRUCTURE OF EDUCATIONAL AND PRODUCTION PRACTICE //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 125-131.
38. Kazakov R. T., Rasulov Q. Q. TRAINING IN INTERNATIONAL WRESTLING TECHNIQUES AND TACTICS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 180-186.
39. Kazoqov R., Akmuradov M. THE IMPORTANCE OF WORKING MEMORY IN MASTERING JUDO SPORTS TECHNIQUES IN ADOLESCENT ATHLETES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 489-494.
40. Kazoqov, R., & Akmuradov, M. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF JUDO. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 481–488.
41. Kazoqov R. T., Umaraliyeva F. T. DRAW A KINESICYCLOGRAM OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING AND BUILD A TIMELINE //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1201-1208.
42. Kazoqov R. T. et al. IMPROVEMENT OF TECHNICAL TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE ATHLETES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1077-1084.
43. Kazoqov R. T. et al. STARTING TECHNIQUE IN SHORT DISTANCE RUNNING //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1070-1076.
44. Xalmuxamedov R. et al. ANALYSIS OF THE DEPENDENCE OF THE CONDITIONS OF THE MIDDLE MOUNTAIN OF INDICATORS OF THE INTENSITY ZONES OF TRAINING TRAINING LOADS OF QUALIFIED BOXER WOMEN //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 473-483.

45. Turdimuratov Y. A. O 'ZBEKISTONDA BOLALAR SPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA OID DAVLAT SIYOSATI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 144-152.
46. Турдимуратов Я. А. КОЧЕВОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО УЗБЕКОВ ЮЖНОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА В КОНЦЕ XIX–НАЧАЛО XX ВВ //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 546-557.
47. Шоймардонов, Ш. А., и др. FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND SKILLS IN STUDENTS. вып. 12, Zenodo, декабрь 2023 г.,
48. Умаров Д. Х., Мусаев Б. Б. Сравнительный анализ структуры нагрузки перспективных юных гимнастов в соревновательном макроцикле //Наука и спорт: современные тенденции. – 2015. – Т. 8. – №. 3. – С. 28-31.
49. Kerimov F. et al. Possible associations of 25 (OH) vitamin D status with upper respiratory tract infections morbidity and overtraining syndrome among elite wrestlers //Journal of Physical Education and Sport. – 2019. – Т. 19. – С. 2177-2184.
50. Умаров Д. Х. СПОРТ ТАКОМИЛЛАШУВ БОСҚИЧИДА СПОРТ ГИМАСТИКАЧИЛАРДА ПСИХОЛОГИК КОМПЛЕКС НАЗОРАТНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Fan-Sportga. – 2022. – №. 1. – С. 31-33.
51. Умаров Д. Х., Холмуродов Л. З., Курбонов Х. Х. СПОРТНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ БОСҚИЧИДА ГИМАСТИКАЧИЛАРНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК НАЗОРАТ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 354-362.
53. Umarov D. X. et al. JISMONIY MASHQLAR YORDAMIDA MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING JISMONIY SIFATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 363-372.
54. Умаров Д. Х., Умаров М. Н., Эштаев А. К. Оздоровительно-развивающие виды основной гимнастики: Учебное пособие //Издательскополграфический отдел УзГос ИФК. – 2006.
55. Bobomurodov A. E. The specific features of agility in preschool children //Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 06. – С. 101-111.
56. Muxitdinovich, F. Y. "Synergetic effect-As an Innovative approach to the Development of the Way of Thinking of Physical Culture and Sports Specialists." *European Journal of Research and Reflections in Education Sciences* 8.12 (2020): 165-170.
57. Якубов, Фазлиддин Мухитдинович. "Бўлажак жисмоний тарбия ва спорт мутахассисларида спорт тафаккури ва унинг услубларини яратиш орқали тафаккур тарзини такомиллаштириш йўллари." *Фан-Спортга* 4 (2019): 17-22.
58. Muqimov, Olim. "СПОРТНИНГ ЖАМИЯТДА ТУТГАН УРНИ ВА ИЖТИМОЙ-ТАРБИЯВИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ." *Физическое воспитание, спорт и здоровье* 1 (2020).